

Virtual Reality Tours of Design Exhibitions and Art Galleries: An Exploratory Experience Assessment in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

To aid sustainability in various sectors including art and design, there have been a growing adoption of various technologies. The integration of Virtual Reality technology into design and art exhibitions and galleries has revolutionised the way audiences engage with designs and other innovative or creative works. This preliminary study explores the satisfaction levels of Nigerian art and design enthusiasts who have experienced VR art galleries and design exhibitions. Utilising a quantitative approach, data were collected from participants through structured questionnaires. Findings reveal a spectrum of satisfaction levels influenced by factors such as prior familiarity with VR technology and the immersive quality of the virtual exhibitions and gallery tours, despite the existing preference for in-person interactions with people, art and designs. The findings reveal that VR possess the potential to enhance design and art appreciation, but points to factors such as usability, technical reliability, and the quality of immersive experiences as core areas for improvement (in the Nigerian context), requiring the inputs of professionals such as Industrial Designers within the VR design sphere. Measures such as the adoption of the hybrid exhibition models, integration of government and private sector involvement, and enhancement of VR quality and interface designs were recommended, with an emphasis on significant increase in sample size for further studies.

Keywords: Art, Design, Gallery, Virtual Reality, Experience.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Advancements in technology are increasingly expanding the role of industrial designers and other professionals like architects and artists in growth and development processes as reflected in various studies (Odji, 2019; Odji, & Oni, 2024; Ughumiakpor & Onoriose, 2025). One of such technologies is virtual reality (VR). Since its inception, VR has significantly transformed human interaction with technology and, as opined by Avilés-Castillo et al. (2025), defining this technology has become a challenge especially because of the assortment of functions and applications it encompasses. VR is an immersive, artificial environment simulated by a computer with real-time interaction, as defined by Bec et al. (2021) and Morimoto et al. (2022). Bryson (2013) had earlier defined VR as the application of computer technology for the creation of interactive three-dimensional spheres in which objects have a sense of spatial presence.

According to Kardong-Edgren et al. (2019), VR is stirring into a chapter of advance innovations and innovative applications for the technology. For instance, the emergence of VR has opened up revolutionary possibilities in a number of industries and fields, including design and the arts (Ahdi et al., 2024; Brenk et al., 2025; Xie, 2025). Users can experience design exhibitions and art displays outside of traditional, onsite exhibition and gallery settings thanks to VR's ability to create immersive, interactive environments. In places like Nigeria, where access to design exhibitions and varied art collections may be restricted for various reasons, this technological development is especially important and groundbreaking.

According to Obadofin & Odji (2025), design exhibitions and art galleries not only serve as vital hubs for the preservation and showcasing Nigeria's diverse artistic, cultural heritage and design prowess, but also are of key economic and social benefit to the nation. However, due to challenges such as logistical and geographic limitations, traditional art and design exhibitions in Nigeria have mostly taken place in physical locations, making them inaccessible to many enthusiasts and, possibly, limiting their potentials. The advent of the VR technology could provide a remedy by enabling remotely accessible virtual product exhibitions and art tours, expanding the audience for art and design.

1.2 Statement of Problem

As noted in studies such as Obasi & Ubani (2025) and Odji (2019), achieving sustainability in any sector often demands the adoption of viable, related technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain technology, the internet of things (IoT), VR and so on. This has inspired the adoption of VR in various sectors. However, despite the fact that there is a growing global adoption of VR technologies in the design, creative and cultural sectors, with an increasing usage in design exhibitions and art shows around the globe (Chang & Suh, 2025; Down, 2023), Nigeria's design exhibitions and art galleries continue to rely heavily on physical visits (Obadofin & Odji, 2025). This limits access for audiences who are constrained by factors such as cost, distance or mobility. In spite of this trend, the Nigerian art scene is beginning to grow toward digital engagement as organisations like the Discovery Museum in Abuja and the Yemisi Shyllon Museum have started incorporating VR to offer immersive historical and artistic experiences space – Figure 1 (Discovery-Museum, 2025; Obadofin & Odji, 2025; Yemisi Shyllon Museum, 2025).

Fig. 1 – A screenshot from the Yemisi Shyllon Museum virtual space (Yemisi Shyllon Museum, 2025).

While these few institutions have begun experimenting with digital showcases, there was (at the time of this study) limited understanding of how Nigerian users actually perceive and experience VR-based tours. The absence of empirical studies on usability/usage, immersion, satisfaction, and overall experiential quality presents a critical gap, making it difficult for

stakeholders to justify investment in VR technologies. Therefore, there is a need to assess users' exploratory experiences with VR tours of design exhibitions and art galleries in Nigeria.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

Premised on the given background, the primary aim of this study was to assess the experiences of Nigerians with VR design and art tours. The specific objectives were to:

- 1) Assess design/art enthusiasts' level of usage of VR technology.
- 2) Determine their level of satisfaction with VR tours compared to onsite design exhibition or gallery tours.
- 3) Examine their attitude towards propagating VR design/art tours.

By assessing the satisfaction levels of Nigerian design and art enthusiasts who have taken part in VR design exhibitions and/or art gallery experiences, this study sought to contribute relevantly to bridging the current research gap within this sphere in Nigeria - presenting a pilot assessment of the experiences of selected design and art enthusiasts with VR, serving as a prelude to a wider study. The research's outcomes were intended to inform the design and implementation of VR design and art exhibitions, with a view to enhancing product and design advancement, enhance cultural engagement and improve accessibility in Nigeria.

2. Methodology

2.1 Methods

This study adopted a quantitative research design (Alford & Teater, 2025) to systematically evaluate the satisfaction of users with VR design and art gallery experiences among Nigerian participants. A structured questionnaire was used to gather data about the participants' demographics, interest in art and design, VR technology familiarity/use, and VR design exhibition and/or art gallery experiences. A two-phase criterion sampling method was adopted. In the first phase, states in the study area were divided into 2 strata, namely: those with significant presence of galleries and design exhibitions and those without. According to Obadofin & Odji (2025), some of the most successful galleries were in the South-West, North-Central and Eastern parts of Nigeria. Hence, study participants were targeted in those regions of the country, including Lagos, Osun, Edo and Abia states including the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, which met the criteria. In the second phase, only 35 participants of the initial

approximately 400 targeted were included in the study, using predetermined selection criteria, such as an interest in art or design, being at least 13 years old and above, having visited a physical art gallery before, being a resident of Nigeria, and being willing to participate in the study, were used to select the participants. The sample size was enough to stabilise the means and sufficient to produce reliable descriptive statistics for the measured variables (i.e. availability/accessibility, satisfaction and usability), although reliability improves with larger sample sizes (Warneke et al., 2025).

Data were collected both online and offline (in cases where participants were easily accessible e.g. in school or at the office) on participants' gender, age, educational background, design or artistic interests, VR familiarity or usage, previous exposure to VR art/design galleries/exhibitions, satisfaction with their VR experiences, as well as their propensity to recommend such VR tours. The study sought to contribute to the larger conversation on digital innovation in design and awareness as well as art appreciation by offering empirical insights into the acceptance and perceived value of VR as a medium for design and art engagement in the Nigerian context. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (including mean, mode and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (including Spearman Correlation Analysis). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Lilliefors correction, Shapiro-Wilk and Anderson-Darling tests were carried out as the need arose.

2.2 Limitations

As insinuated by Lakens (2022), appropriate sample sizes aid the accuracy, integrity and low error rate in a study. A notable limitation of this study was its rather small sample size which, according to Warneke et al. (2025), may diminish the reliability and generalisability of the study outcome. Besides, inappropriately small sample sizes may also make it difficult to detect true effects i.e. false negatives or type II errors as well as upsurge the risk of random variability (Lakens, 2022; Moussa & Al-Nersh, 2025; Weichenthal et al., 2017). Such studies as this may not only benefit from a larger sample size, but also from a larger scope. However, this study was only a preliminary study conducted on a small-scale to evaluate feasibility, possible cost, duration, adverse events and improve upon the study design prior to performance of a larger-scaled study.

3. Results

3.1 Demographics

Only 31 of the 35 participants who were sampled gave valid answers, and 4 responses were disqualified for having insufficient or conflicting information. Hence, the pool of valid study participants consisted of a total of 15 females and 16 males, aged between 14 and 53 years (Figure 1 and Table 1).

Fig. 1 – Gender distribution of study participants

As shown in Table 1, with a mean age of 16.18 and a small range of 3 years, the 11 members of the "Under 18" group showed little age variation. With a mean age of 21.55 and a higher standard deviation (2.46), the "18–25" group also consists of 11 people, but their range was wider by 7 years, indicating greater age dispersion.

Table 1 – Age distribution of the participants

Age Range	Frequency	Mean Age	Median Age	Mode Age	Std. Dev.	Age Range (Max - Min)
Under 18	11	16.18	16.0	17	0.98	3
18–25	11	21.55	22.0	18	2.46	7
26–40	5	33.80	35.0	40	6.57	14
41 and above	4	47.50	48.0	41	5.92	12

With ages ranging from 14 to 40, the "26–40" group was smaller (5 people), but it had the highest standard deviation (6.57), indicating significant variation. Lastly, there were only 4 people in the "41 and above" group, and their mean age being 47.50 with a range of 12 years, indicating a moderate age spread. While older groups exhibited greater age dispersion but fewer individuals, younger groups generally had higher frequencies and less variations. In terms of level of education (Figure 2), the majority of the participants (18) were undergraduates, 10 were postgraduates, while only 3 persons had only a secondary education. This suggests a highly educated sample, with most individuals having at least some higher education experience or qualifications.

Fig. 2 – Educational distribution of study participants

3.2 Interest in Design Exhibitions or Art Galleries

The interests of the participants were sampled and the results were as shown in Figure 3. Most of the participants (22) were "Interested," followed by 6 who claimed to be "Very Interested." Only 3 of the participants claimed to be only "Somewhat Interested" in art or design. This suggests a strong overall interest in art and design, with only a small portion showing lower enthusiasm. One key trend was that younger people, particularly secondary and undergraduate students who participated in the study, were typically "Interested" in art and design but infrequently exhibit "Very Interested" levels. Postgraduates were more likely to be "Very Interested," indicating a deeper engagement with art and design at higher educational levels, especially those who are older (i.e. aged 40+).

Fig. 3 – Participants levels of interests in design or art exhibitions and galleries.

3.3 Participants’ Familiarity with or Frequency of Usage of VR Technology

Figure 4 is a reflection of the level of familiarity (in terms of frequency of usage) that the study participants had with VR. The findings indicate that a majority of participants had prior experience with VR, with 51.6% using it occasionally and 35.5% frequently, while only 12.9% had never used it. The mean score of 1.77 suggests an inclination towards occasional use, and a standard deviation of 0.67 reflects moderate variability in familiarity among participants. Although most were familiar with VR, the presence of first-time users suggests a need for basic orientation to enhance engagement.

Fig. 4 – Participants’ level of familiarity with the VR technology.

3.3.1 Comparing Participants’ Familiarity/Usage with Interest in Design and Art Products or Pieces

The interest in design exhibitions and art pieces of the respondents were compared with their familiarity/usage of VR technology. This was to establish if there was any correlation between both variables – interest in design and art pieces and familiarity/usage of VR technology. The results were as summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 – Comparing familiarity/usage with interest in design and art products or pieces

		Interest in Design and Art Products or Pieces			
		Respectively			
		Interested	Very Interested	Somewhat Interested	Total
Familiarity With VR Technology	Frequently	10	1	0	11
	Occasionally	11	5	0	16
	Never used prior to this study	1	0	3	4
Total		22	6	3	31

The findings indicate a clear relationship between participants’ familiarity with VR technology and their level of interest in design and art products. Those who are interested or very interested in design appear to have higher levels of VR usage, as seen in the fact that the majority of frequent and occasional users fall within these two interest categories. Specifically, among the “interested” group (n = 22), most participants use VR either frequently or occasionally, reflected by their mean familiarity score of 1.59, indicating relatively high exposure. The “very interested” group (n = 6) also shows moderate VR engagement, with a mean of 1.83, suggesting occasional use is most common. In contrast, participants who are only “somewhat interested” (n = 3) show no meaningful VR experience—having a mean score of 3.0—and all fall into the “never used” category. The mode values reinforce this pattern, with modes of 2 for both the interested and very interested groups (indicating occasional use), and a mode of 3 for the somewhat interested group (indicating no prior use). Overall, the findings suggest that higher interest in design and art is associated with greater familiarity and engagement with VR technology, while low interest corresponds with minimal or no VR exposure.

Table 3 – Comparing familiarity/usage with interest in design and art products or pieces

		Frequency	Mean	Mode	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Familiarity With VR Technology	Interested	22	1.59	2	0.59	1	3
	Very Interested	6	1.83	2	0.41	1	2
	Somewhat Interested	3	3	3	0	3	3

3.3.2 Comparing Participants’ Familiarity/Usage with Level of Education

The respondents’ familiarity/usage of VR technology was also compared with their level of education. This was to establish if there was any correlation between both variables – education and familiarity/usage of VR technology. The results were as summarised in Tables 4, 5 and 6, with an assumption tests for normality and spearman correlation analysis conducted.

Table 4 – Comparing familiarity/usage with level of education

		Educational Level			
		Secondary	Undergraduate	Postgraduate	Total
Familiarity With VR Technology	Frequently	2	6	3	11
	Occasionally	1	11	4	16
	Never used prior to this study	0	1	3	4
	Total	3	18	10	31

The study's results indicate a correlation between educational level and familiarity with VR technology. Among postgraduate respondents, 3 indicated frequent use of VR, 4 reported occasional use, and 3 had never utilized VR prior to the study. Undergraduates exhibited moderate VR exposure, with 11 reporting occasional use and 6 reporting frequent use. Secondary school participants demonstrated the least familiarity. This trend suggests that higher academic achievement is associated with increased exposure to VR, likely due to better access to digital tools, academic necessities, or involvement in tech-oriented settings.

Table 5 – Tests for normal distribution of level of education and familiarity with virtual reality

	Educational Level		Familiarity With VR Technology	
	Statistics	p	Statistics	p
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.32	.003	0.28	.013
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors Corr.)	0.32	<.001	0.28	<.001
Shapiro-Wilk	0.77	<.001	0.79	<.001
Anderson-Darling	3.55	<.001	3.02	<.001

The assumption tests for normality revealed that both educational level and VR familiarity are not normally distributed, as all four tests (Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Lilliefors correction, Shapiro-Wilk, and Anderson-Darling) produced statistically significant p-values ($p < .05$). These violations justified the use of a nonparametric test, such as Spearman’s correlation (Table 6).

Table 6 – Spearman’s Correlation

	r	p
Educational Level and Familiarity with VR Technology	0.26	.154

The Spearman correlation result (Table 6) indicates a positive but weak relationship between educational level and familiarity with VR. However, the relationship is not statistically significant, suggesting that while higher education levels tend to be associated with higher VR exposure, this association is not strong enough to be considered reliable within this sample. In essence, the findings imply that education may play a role in VR familiarity, but other factors—such as personal interest, access to technology, or socioeconomic background—may be more influential.

3.4 Comparing Participants’ Accessibility to VR Technology

The results show that 57.1% of participants reported moderate accessibility to VR technology, while 32.1% had high access, and 10.7% indicated low or no access (Table 7). The mean score of 1.79 indicates a general trend toward moderate or average access level, with a standard deviation of 0.63 reflecting moderate variability among responses. In all, while most

participants have adequate access to VR technology, access levels are not uniformly high, and a minority face significant limitations that could impact their engagement in VR activities.

Table 7 – Access to VR Technology

Accessibility To VR Technology	Frequency	Mode	Mean	Std. Dev.
High	9	2	1.79	0.63
Moderate	16			
Low or none	3			
Total	28			
Invalid	3			
Total	31			

3.4.1 Participants’ Accessibility to VR Technology and VR Exposure/Familiarity/Usage

The respondents’ familiarity/usage of VR technology was also compared with their level of education. This was to establish if there was any correlation between both variables – education and familiarity/usage of VR technology. The results were as summarised in Tables 8, 9 and 10, with an assumption tests for normality and spearman correlation analysis conducted.

Table 8 – Comparing familiarity/usage with level of education

		Familiarity with VR Technology			
		Frequently	Occasionally	Never used prior to this study	Total
Accessibility To VR Technology	High	9	0	0	9
	Moderate	2	14	0	16
	Low or none	0	2	1	3
	Total	11	16	1	28

The results show a strong and consistent relationship between accessibility to VR technology and familiarity with its use. Participants with high accessibility all reported frequent VR usage, indicating that ready access directly supports regular engagement. Those with moderate

accessibility largely reported occasional usage, suggesting that even partial access enables meaningful but less frequent interaction with VR. In contrast, participants with low or no accessibility demonstrated minimal VR exposure. This distribution shows a clear gradient—higher accessibility corresponds with higher familiarity and usage, while limited access restricts VR experience.

The normality tests (Table 9) showed that accessibility and familiarity with VR do not follow a normal distribution, justifying the use of the Spearman rank-order correlation (Table 10).

Table 9 – Tests for normal distribution of level of education and familiarity with virtual reality

	Familiarity With VR Technology		Accessibility to VR Technology	
	Statistics	p	Statistics	p
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.28	.013	0.31	.006
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors Corr.)	0.28	<.001	0.31	<.001
Shapiro-Wilk	0.79	<.001	0.78	<.001
Anderson-Darling	3.02	<.001	3.08	<.001

A strong positive relationship was found ($r = 0.84, p < .001$), indicating that greater access to VR significantly enhances users' familiarity and interaction with the technology. The findings underscore the importance of accessibility in shaping users' VR experiences, suggesting that improvements in access can boost proficiency and comfort with VR systems.

Table 10 – Spearman's Correlation

	r	p
Educational Level and Familiarity with VR Technology	0.26	.154

3.5 Experience Assessment

To comparatively access the VR and onsite experiences of the study participants, it was necessary to ascertain if they had had both VR and onsite gallery/exhibition experiences.

Fig. 5 – Participants’ experience with VR and onsite galleries/exhibitions.

As showed in Figure 5 above, only 4 of the participants had not both visited a gallery or taken its virtual tour, whereas a sizable majority (27 of the participants) had both visited a gallery and taken its virtual tour. This shows that people who visit galleries are also receptive to exploring them online, suggesting a significant overlap between in-person and virtual gallery experiences. Among those that already had experience with VR art and design tours, the level of experience differed. Noticeably, people who had previously used VR technology were more likely to find the virtual design and art tours enjoyable.

In terms of satisfaction derived, as shown in Table 11, 9 of the participants’ were "Satisfied" with VR design and art gallery tours they had participated in, citing factors such as immersive experience, while eleven were "Very Dissatisfied," citing factors such as sensory limitations and sporadic technical issues as downsides of VR usage and preferred onsite gallery visits. Even those with mixed or unfavourable experiences found VR design exhibitions and art gallery tours valuable, as evidenced by the majority (19 out of 28) who would still recommend them to others.

Table 11 - Level of Satisfaction and Influence on Attitude towards Propagating Awareness for VR Design and Art Tours/Exhibitions.

Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Would Recommend	Would Not Recommend
Very Satisfied	2	1	1
Satisfied	9	9	0
Dissatisfied	1	1	0
Very Dissatisfied	11	8	3
No Response	5	0	5
Total	28	19	9

Interestingly, 8 out of the 11 "Very Dissatisfied" study participants still supported awareness efforts, indicating that dissatisfaction does not completely discourage advocacy for VR design and art tours. All "Satisfied" respondents would readily recommend the tours. The five respondents who did not reply, however, also did not recommend, suggesting a potential link between disengagement and reluctance to advertise VR design exhibition and art gallery tours.

4. Discussion

By fusing traditional experiences with technological innovation, the incorporation of VR into art and design gallery tours and exhibitions in Nigeria has opened up new ways to appreciate and participate in art and design in Nigeria. This study explored at how satisfied participants were with VR art and design tours/exhibitions and whether they are inclined to recommend them.

4.1 Usage of VR Technology in Nigeria

As can be deduced from the findings of studies from various fields of research, the level of familiarity with a technology like VR often influences usage or adoption (Horowitz et al., 2024; Shen et al., 2022; Tavitiyaman et al., 2022). The familiarity levels of this study’s participants with VR technology varied. Some respondents had never used VR before the study, even though all of them indicated an interest in art and design. This reveals a lack of awareness and accessibility regarding VR, indicating the necessity of educational programs and user-friendly interfaces to facilitate the adoption of virtual art experiences. Prior VR exposure has a significant impact on engagement levels, according to studies such as Anaya-Sánchez et al.

(2024) and Chang & Suh (2025), with seasoned users demonstrating greater comfort and appreciation for immersive exhibitions. This is consistent with this study's findings, which showed that people who were familiar with VR had more affinity for virtual design exhibitions and art tours.

4.2 Satisfaction with VR Tours and Exhibitions vs. Onsite Gallery Visits

Participants' satisfaction levels with VR art and design tours varied significantly. Some of them found VR's immersive and interactive features to be captivating, which might have improved their familiarity and understanding of artworks and designs outside of conventional contexts. Others, however, cited sensory limitations and sporadic technical issues as disadvantages and preferred in-person gallery visits. The findings indicated that people who had previously used VR were more likely to find the tours enjoyable, whereas people who had never used the technology before expressed less satisfaction. Cheng et al. (2024) found similar results, indicating that satisfaction with VR exhibitions is significantly influenced by expectation confirmation. While VR does not completely replace the tactile and spatial experience of physical art galleries and design exhibitions, it nonetheless provides accessibility and convenience, especially for users who are located far away or have challenges accessing the galleries or exhibitions physically.

4.3 Attitude towards Promoting VR Design and Art Tours

A sizable portion of participants indicated a willingness to promote VR art tours, despite varying degrees of satisfaction. All of the participants who expressed satisfaction with the experience noted that they would recommend it to others. It is interesting to note that even some seemingly 'dissatisfied' participants recognised the potential of VR and backed raising awareness on it in Nigeria. This implies that although advocacy is influenced by user experience as insinuated in studies such as Getto & Flanagan (2022) and Martin et al. (2017), additional elements — like improvements in accessibility, technological advancements, and exposure to top-notch VR content—may promote adoption even more. Cheng et al. (2024) also stress that the immersive quality and perceived utility of VR art exhibitions are powerful drivers of ongoing participation and promotion.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The study findings showed that while participants' familiarity with VR technology varied, they were all interested in art or design. The findings emphasised the need for user-friendly VR experiences because some people had never used it. Some of the participants expressed high levels of satisfaction with virtual gallery and exhibition tours because of their immersive experience, while others expressed dissatisfaction because of technical issues or a preference for in-person interactions with people, art and designs/products. There was a mixed response to the question of whether or not to recommend VR design and art tours. While the findings point to the potential of VR technology to completely transform the design/art gallery and exhibition landscape in Nigeria, they nonetheless also emphasise some core limitations. Although VR in design/art exhibitions offers new ways to interact, yet factors like usability, technical reliability, and the quality of immersive experiences determine how satisfied users will be or can be.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations, with implications for practice and further study, are proposed:

- 1) Improvement of the availability/accessibility of VR facilities: Since findings indicated that people who had previously used VR technology were more likely to find the virtual design exhibitions and art tours enjoyable, there is therefore the need for improvement in public VR facilities for easy access to VR design and art exhibitions/galleries. This should involve both the government and private sector participants.
- 2) Improvement of VR quality and user-friendliness: Creation of intuitive, high-resolution, interactive VR experiences compatible with accessible devices. Industrial Designers, especially those within the Graphic sphere, have forefront roles to play in achieving this. While VR is not art or culture in itself (as it falls within the confines of technologists, designers and programmers), it can go a long way in helping art and design galleries and exhibitions achieve their purpose more effectively and holistically in Nigeria as well as in any other society globally, if properly embraced and harnessed. While improved accessibility may help build positive expectations as suggested by

Cheng et al. (2024), improved user-friendliness and quality should aid the optimisation of satisfactions or utility derived.

- 3) Integration of hybrid exhibition models: Rather merely organising physical exhibitions onsite, an improved approach will be to combine physical and virtual design and art experiences for holistic appreciation.
- 4) Increase awareness and education: There is also the need for implementation of public awareness campaigns, school programs, and workshops to educate the public about VR in art and design.
- 5) Encouragement of government and private sector investment: Provision of support for VR-based art initiatives through grants, sponsorships, and collaborations to foster innovation and preserve cultural heritage. Institutions offering design and art related courses may also invest, both financially and research-wise, into building and optimising VR facilities for improved accessibility.
- 6) A larger scaled study should also include factors such as level of ‘immersion’, while the sample size should also be scaled up significantly to improve reliability and generalisability (Warneke et al., 2025).

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